

A STUDY ON CONSUMER PREFERENCE TOWARDS ‘AMUL PRODUCT’ IN MADURAI CITY

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Abstract:

Amul (Anand milk produced union limited) formed in 1946, is a diary co operative movement in India. The brand name Amul sourced from the Sanskrit word Amoolya means priceless. India largest food brand trusted Amul product for its quality and product available at affordable price. Amul has different type such as milk, chocolate, milk powder, curd, ice cream etc., Amul has strong network of over 3million milk producer. Amul product has a good reputation among the customers in Madurai. Amul product already enjoying No.1 position in diary industry, this gives a positive stand to further strengthen its position. This research is pertaining to find out the present consumer satisfaction of Amul product.

Introduction:

Amul spurred India's *White Revolution*, which made the country the world's largest producer of milk and milk products. In the process Amul became the largest food brand in India and has also ventured into markets overseas. Dr. Verghese Kurien, founder-chairman of the GCMMF for more than 30 years (1973-2006), is credited with the success of Amul. The Gujarat Co-operative Milk Marketing Federation Ltd. (GCMMF), which today is jointly owned by 3.03 million milk producers in Gujarat. A key achievement at Amul was the invention of milk powder processed from buffalo-milk abundant in India as opposed to that made from cow-milk in the major milk producing nation. Amul has different type such as milk, chocolate, milk powder, curd, ice cream etc., Amul has strong network of over 3million milk producer. Britannia industry and nestle Ltd. are competitive product for Amul. India largest food brand trusted Amul product for its quality and product available at affordable price. Number of popular milk product like Ice cream, Butter and Curd prefer to use Amul rather than other product. In this context, the study is aim to analyze the customer satisfaction towards Amul product in Madurai.

Statement of the Problem:

Amul (Anand milk produced union limited) formed in 1946, is a diary co operative movement in India. The brand name Amul sourced from the Sanskrit word Amoolya means priceless. Amul product has different type such as Milk, Chocolate, Milk powder, Curd, Ice cream etc., Amul has strong network of over 3 million milk producer. Britannia industry and nestle Ltd. are competitive product for Amul. Amul is a world's largest manufacturer of pouched milk. India largest food brand trusted Amul product for its quality and product available at affordable price. Number of popular milk product like Ice cream, Butter and Curd prefer to use Amul rather than other product. This research is pertaining to find out the present consumer satisfaction of Amul product.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To enhance the image of Amul company
- ✓ To study the customer preference towards Amul product
- ✓ To give necessary suggestion on the basis of findings of the study.

Profile of the Respondents:

The respondents are Amul product user of different Age group, Education, Gender, Marital status, Number of member, Monthly income level, Sales promotional activities.

Age Wise Classification of the Respondents: The respondents were classified on the basis of their age. Age wise classification of the sample respondents is given in the Table.

Age Wise Classification of the Respondents		
Age	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
20-30years	68	68
31-40years	20	20
Above41years	12	12
Total	100	100

It is inferred from the above table 3.1 shows that,68% of the respondents are belong to the age of 20-30years,20% of the respondents are belong to the age of 31-40years and 12% of the respondents are above41years.

Gender Wise Classification of the Respondents: The respondents were classified on the basis of their gender .They were grouped under two categories. Gender wise classification of the sample respondents is given in the Table.

Gender Wise Classification of the Respondents		
Gender	No of Respondent	% of Respondents
Male	39	39
Female	61	61
Total	100	100

From the above table 3.2 shows that, 61%of the respondents are female and remaining 39% of the respondents are male.

Type of Family: The respondents were classified on the basis of their family members. They were grouped under two categories family wise classification of the sample respondents is given in the table

Type of Family		
Type of Family	No. of Respondent	%of Respondents
Joint Family	44	44
Nuclear Family	56	56
Total	100	100

It is inferred from the above table, showing that 56% of the respondents live as in nuclear family and 44% of the respondents live as in joint family.

Family Members: The respondents were classified on the basis of their Number of members in a family. They were grouped under four categories. Family member wise of the sample respondents is given in the Table.

Family Members		
Members in a Family	No. of Respondent	% of Respondents
Below 2	6	6
3 to 5	50	50
Above 5	44	44
Total	100	100

It is inferred from the above table, showing that 50% of the respondents having members of 3 to 5, 44% of the respondents having members of above 5 and 6% of respondents having member of below 2.

Income Wise Classification: The respondents were classified on the basis of their Monthly Income. They were grouped under three categories. Income wise classification of the sample respondents is the given in the table.

Income Wise Classification		
Monthly Income	No. of Respondent	% of Respondents
Up to Rs 5000	11	11
Rs5001-Rs10000	26	26
Above Rs.10001	63	63
Total	100	100

It is observed from the Table , out of 100 respondents 63% of the respondents are earn monthly income Above Rs.10001,26% of the respondents earn an monthly income Between Rs.5001 to Rs.10000 and 11% of the respondents earn a monthly income below Rs.5000.

Aware of the Product: The respondents were classified on the basis of their Awareness of the product. Classification of the respondents based on awareness of the product is given in the Table.

Awareness of the Product		
Awareness	No. of Respondent	% of Respondents
Yes	92	92
No	8	8
Total	100	100

It is observed from the above table, shows that, 92% of the respondents were aware of the product and 8% of the respondents were not aware of the products.

Types of Amul Product: The respondents were classified on the basis of their Amul product. They were grouped under six categories Amul product wise classification of the sample respondents is given in the table

Types of Amul Product		
Types of Amul Product	No of Respondents	% of Respondents
Chocolate	20	20
Milk	29	29
Ice-cream	25	25
Butter	9	9
Milk Powder	9	9

Curd	8	8
Total	100	100

It is observed from the table, out of 100 respondents, 29% of respondents using milk, 25% of respondents using ice-cream, 20% of respondents using chocolate, 9% of respondents using Butter and milk powder and 8% of respondents using curd.

Duration of Usage: The respondents were classified on the basis of their usage. Year wise classification of the sample respondents is given in the table.

Duration of Usage		
No of Years	No. of Respondent	% of Respondents
Below 1 year	52	52
More than 1 year	34	34
More than 5years	14	14
Total	100	100

It is observed from the above table, out of 100 respondents.52% of the respondents are using Amul product below 1year,34% of the respondents are using Amul product more than 1 years and 14% of the respondents are using Amul product more than 5 years.

Sources of Information: The respondents were classified on the basis of their mode of sources; the classification of the respondents is given in the table.

Sources of Information		
Sources of Information	No of Respondents	% of Respondents
Television	58	58
Newspaper	19	19
Broucher	12	12
Display	11	11
Total	100	100

It is inferred from the above table, showing that 58% of the respondents knowing information through television,19% of the respondents knowing through news paper 12% of the respondents knowing through broucher and 11% of the respondents through display.

Place of Purchase: The respondents were classified on the basis of their place of purchase. Place of purchase wise classification of the respondents is given in the Table.

Place of Purchase		
Places	No of Respondents	% of Respondents
Departmental Store	48	48
Retail Shop	33	33
Petty Shop	12	12
Super Market	7	7
Total	100	100

It is observed that 48% of the respondents are buying Amul product from Departmental store,33% of the respondents are buying Amul product from Retail shop,12% of the respondents are buying Amul product from Petty shop and 7% of the respondents are buying Amul product from Super market.

Size of Packet: The size of the packet categorized into four is given in the table.

Size of Packet		
Size	No. of Respondent	% of Respondents
Small Pack	42	42
Big Pack	24	24
Family Pack	34	34
Total	100	100

It is observed from the above table. 42% of the respondents are using small size packet, 34% of the respondents are using family size packet, and 24% of the respondents are using big size packet.

Duration of Purchase: The respondents were classified on the basis of their purchase duration. They were grouped under four categorized. The classification of the respondents is given in the table.

Duration of Purchase		
Duration	No. of Respondent	% of Respondents
Daily	44	44
Weekly	25	25
Monthly	26	26
Quarterly	5	5
Total	100	100

It is inferred from the above table, showing that 44% of the respondents are purchasing Amul product daily, 26% of the respondents are purchasing Amul product on monthly basis, 25% of the respondents are purchasing Amul product weekly and 5% of the respondents are purchasing quarterly.

Preference to Buy Amul Product: The respondents were classified on the basis of their preference. They were grouped under three categories. Classification of the respondents is given in the table.

Preference to Buy Amul Product		
Preference of Product	No. of Respondent	% of Respondents
Price Off	39	39
Free Sample	32	32
Discount	29	29
Total	100	100

It is inferred from the above table 3.16 showing that 39% of the respondents are prefer Amul product due to price off, 32% of the respondents are prefer Amul product due to free sample and 29% of the respondents are prefer Amul product due to discount.

Recommendation of Product: The respondents were classified on the basis of their recommendation of Amul product. They were grouped under two categories. Recommendation wise classification of the sample respondents is given in the table.

Recommendation of Product		
Recommendation	No. of Respondent	% of Respondents
Yes	68	68
No	32	32
Total	100	100

It is observed that 68% of the respondents were recommended Amul products and 32% of the respondents were not ready to recommend the Amul products to others.

Level of Satisfaction on the Basis of Amul Product: An attempt has been made to analyse the satisfaction towards Amul product. Weighted averages are used to analyse the satisfaction level.

HS - Highly Satisfied; S – Satisfied; N - Neutral; DS - Dis Satisfied; HDS - Highly Dissatisfied; WAG - Weighted Average

Level of Satisfaction Towards Amul Product								
Particulars	HS	S	N	DS	HDS	Total	WAG	Rank
Price	205 (41)	212 (53)	147 (49)	86 (43)	57 (57)	707	7.07	I
Quality	225 (45)	144 (36)	84 (28)	82 (41)	33 (33)	568	5.68	II
Available	35 (7)	24 (6)	54 (18)	24 (12)	6 (6)	143	1.43	III
Package	30 (6)	12 (3)	9 (3)	4 (2)	2 (2)	57	0.57	IV
Taste	5 (1)	8 (2)	6 (2)	4 (2)	2 (2)	25	0.25	V

With regard to the level satisfaction towards Amul product “The price of Amul product” has secured highest value of 707. “The quality of Amul product” has secured the second place with the value of 568. “Available of Amul product” has secured the third place with the value of 143. “Package of Amul product” has secured the fourth place with the value of 57 and “Taste of Amul product” has considered lastly with the value of 25.

Suggestion:

The analysis, findings and observation during the customer satisfaction survey is the basis for suggestion. These have been made after considering the percentages.

- ✓ Most of the respondents purchasing milk chocolate and butter so it should be motivated to buy other product also.
- ✓ The respondents who earn an income of above Rs. 10001 purchasing Amul product. So it is suggested to provide various offers.
- ✓ With regard to the level of satisfaction package got IV and Taste got V place so it is suggested to improve their package style.
- ✓ Few of the respondents satisfied with the taste of Amul product so it should be concentrate on improving their taste by adding some more Ingredients and Flavours.

Conclusion:

Amul product has a good reputation among the customers in Madurai. So it can be extended to supply rural area also. From various respondents the researcher has gathered lot of information's among Amul product's

buying behaviour. Amul product already enjoying No.1 position in diary industry, this gives a positive stand to further strengthen its position. It was concluded that "Amul product is the market leader in diary industry".

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